

Quantum Momentum Scaling px and Special Relativity

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 13, 2022

The classical action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) may be written with $v=x/t$ and x and t varied independently to yield $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$. Thus $A = -Et+px$ is a solution. This expression also appears in classical wave forms and in the electromagnetic description of a photon (from Maxwell's laws). $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant and so is directly linked to special relativity and different frames moving with constant velocity. In (1) we argued that x and t should be treated as independent in A . This suggests that p is a scaling in space and E in time. Thus there should be physical lengths proportional to $1/p$ and physical time intervals proportional to $1/E$.

Special relativity considers different frames (moving with constant velocity) and 4-vectors so it seems to be quite different from a scenario with t and x separated and scaling of x by p . We argue that although $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant and as such may be used to find $E(v)$ and $p(v)$, quantum mechanics is usually performed in a special frame, namely one in which $V(x)$ or $V(x,v)$ the potential is at rest. (For electromagnetism one treats (A, ϕ) as a 4-vector, but this is not the norm.) As a result, energy E_n found in a rest frame of the potential also represents "rest energy" so E_n is binding energy which is added to rest mass energy. In other words motion in the rest frame of a potential creates rest energy = rest mass.

We argue that $V(x)$ may be written as a sum over k $V_k \exp(ikx)$ and so no time related terms appear, only momentum linked ones. Thus momentum is the key feature for the interaction, even though velocity and time are still in the picture (just sometimes not directly in the interaction scheme). For example, a two slit interference or single slit diffraction does not depend on time or speed although these are certainly in the problem. For a bound state v and t are also in the problem as one calculates average kinetic energy using $pp/2m = .5 p v$ which is rate dependent, but there is no acceleration which is a time-dependent phenomenon. Rather one deals with an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$'s because these interact with the potential in a wavelike manner to create the effect of acceleration. $\exp(ipx)$ a momentum wave linked to the scaling of x by p in px is not only involved in an interaction with $V(x)$, but represents extra information from the classical mechanical picture. $\exp(ipx)$ for a known rest mass m_0 means one knows $v=x/t=dx/dt$, yet there is an extra piece of information namely the phase px which is involved in even "free" interactions such as two identical particle with different phases arriving at the same x at the same t or the average kinetic energy in a bound state. Velocity v is converted into a momentum expression through p/m_0 in the nonrelativistic case and so $\exp(ipx)$ governs the whole scenario. Acceleration then becomes a mathematical abstraction of the motion of $v_{rms}(x)$ for any quantum bound energy level with the real physics associated with $\exp(ipx)$ being ignored.

Classical Action and Special Relativity

The classical action of a free quantum particle is $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2}$ relativistically ($c=1$) or $A = .5m v^2$ nonrelativistically. Using $v=x/t$ and treating x and t as independent leads to:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ ((1a)) and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \text{ ((1b))}$$

As a result $A = -Et + px$ is a solution, but this is a Lorentz invariant. Lorentz transformations, however, are used to transform 4-vectors such as (x,t) or (p,E) to describe how they would be viewed from a frame moving at a constant v . In (1), however, we suggested that px means p scales x and that this should be physically manifested. (Also E scales t .) This is a separate idea from special relativity and leads to the idea of a wavelength. At the same time $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $E = m_0 + .5pv$ to first order which follow directly from special relativity and x and t not being treated independently. This seems like a contradiction, but $\exp(ipx)$ with its modulus of 1 allows for nonlocality i.e. wavelengths and no apparent time, but at the same time, creates the sense of $x=vt$ through the modulus of 1 because one considers two shifted spatial distributions (i.e. one representing one time and the other a later time) i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$.

The form $A = -Et + px$ may be used with $dA=0$ for $-t dE/dv + x dp/dv$ and $p=Ev$ to determine the relativistic relationship $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ $c=1$. This is used in a quantum mechanical calculation, but it seems that in quantum mechanics one usually chooses a special frame, namely the rest frame of the potential $V(x)$ or $V(x,v)$. (We do not consider $V(x,t)$ here.) $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ so time does not appear explicitly. Thus we argue that $V(x)$ potentials are momentum related. Even though time t and velocity v exist in the problem, they do not govern how the potential interacts with the particle unlike in the Newtonian picture in which there is acceleration within a tiny dx . For example, if one considers single slit diffraction or two slit interference $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ means that two very different velocities (and hence) times have the same momentum and yield the same diffraction pattern. The pattern is due to the interaction of the particle with a potential in an unusual way i.e. a probabilistic wave manner adding $\exp(ipx)$ as an OR probability for different possibilities, but time and velocity do not enter. It seems that a very fast moving particle would undergo its potential interaction quickly, but this does not change the result of the interaction - it is momentum dependent.

A similar result holds for a bound state in which the interaction with $V(x)$ is completely momentum dependent. Velocity and time, however, are present in the problem. A particle with momentum p has kinetic energy $.5pv$ which is rate dependent. In Newtonian mechanics, one considers $v(x)$ and allows it to change within each dx . Thus force (or potential) changes the velocity within each dx . In quantum mechanics the picture is different because an $\exp(ikx)$ from $V_k \exp(ikx)$ exists in all of space and is like a momentum wave. It interacts with $\exp(ipx)$ s which are only momentum dependent. $V(x)$ as an average, however, must be added to an average kinetic energy to yield a constant E_n just as in classical mechanics. Kinetic energy by definition is velocity or rate dependent i.e. $.5pv$. A particle with momentum p in quantum mechanics and m_0 has a well defined velocity. This velocity is even related to its kinetic energy, but not directly (but indirectly) to its interaction with the potential $V(x)$. In fact, one uses a distribution of $\exp(ipx)$'s to allow for momentum interactions with $V(x)$. Each $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to a kinetic energy (velocity dependent) of $.5pv$, but has a total energy of E_n not $pp/2m$.

To see this, consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$. For each $\exp(ipx)$ one has:

$$a(p) .5pv + \text{Sum over } k \ V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \text{ ((2))}$$

The second term on the LHS shows that $V(x)$ only interacts through momentum and is not affected directly by velocity. This creates a potential due to interactions with all $\exp(ipx)$'s, but a specific $\exp(ipx)$ still has a velocity dependent energy term $\frac{1}{2}pv$ $a(p)$. Thus ((2)) is a hybrid of momentum based interaction with $V(x)$ and rate dependent kinetic energy pieces. The idea seems to be that the potential can only interact with momentum and give impulse hits so one does not have a single p accelerating in space. Rather momentum wave type conditional probabilities $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)\}$ govern how the kinetic energy changes from one x to another. In other words quantum bound states have velocity v and time, but interactions only occur through momentum hits and there are no higher derivatives such as acceleration which would allow one to follow a particle in space and time. In the next section we consider the effect of $\exp(ipx)$ on free motion and interference even for a kinetic term.

Velocity in Quantum Mechanics

Above it was noted how the potential $V(x)$ interacts through momentum in particular through an $\exp(ikx)$ type of wave. The particle is also described in terms of $\exp(ipx)$.

P , however, is a function of v (velocity) through a relationship based on $-Et+px$ and $p=Ev$. So why does one not simply consider motion via $x(t)$ as in classical mechanics? It seems that the $\exp(ipx)$ form contains more information than $x(t)$. P in $\exp(ipx)$ makes use of knowledge of m_0 and $v=dx/dt$, but it has an additional piece of information namely px , a phase which does not appear in classical mechanics. This phase is linked to p scaling x . $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of probability which includes motion so one does not have the classical picture of a particle only existing and translating as a point. There is wave nonlocality in $\cos(px)$, but by considering a shift in space (i.e. also time) one may describe motion strictly in terms of space while still including the idea of a phase px . Thus a free particle described by $\exp(ipx)$ (modulus 1) has p and $p^2/2m$ at each x point, but still keeps track of phase which leads to a kind of interaction even without a specific potential. For example, if two identical particles with the same p , but a phase shift arrive at the same point at the same time, they will "interfere" i.e. a reaction will occur. Thus free motion and even $\frac{1}{2}pv$ is linked to possible free interference. The modulus of 1 associated with $\exp(ipx)$ gives the illusion of locality i.e. for all situations. For a free noninterfering particle this is the case and hence the Newtonian picture applies. If interference, however, occurs then even free motion linked with $\frac{1}{2}pv$ is associated with interference.

For a bound system the average kinetic energy consists of the interference of various $\frac{1}{2}pv$ $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ terms. In such a case time is removed from the picture and v is written as p/m_0 so one may use $p=-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx)$. As a result, $\exp(ipx)$ governs even free type of motion i.e. $\frac{1}{2}pv$ terms and is involved in interference interactions which differ from interactions with $V(x)$, but are still based on $\exp(ipx)$. It should be noted that velocity does not disappear from the problem. $p=m_0v_1=m_0v_2$ are the same in $\exp(ipx)$, but the presence of mass in $v=p/m$ means that E_n distinguishes mass. Thus overall it not just momentum which governs the final answer i.e. E_n , m_0 is also present.

Interestingly the average $KE(x) = \{-\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W\} = KE(x)$ classical means $v_{rms}(x)$ behaves as if it were accelerating and there were no $\exp(ipx)$ in the picture. In other words the momentum wave is able to create the illusion of acceleration for any quantum energy level without time being explicitly present in the bound state calculation.

It is possible for a potential to be velocity dependent as in the case of nucleons. For that situation, one may use $(-i\hbar/dx)$ in the potential so it is a function of x and d/dx . The idea of the quantum calculation being performed in the rest frame of the nucleus still applies and E_n is still a binding energy.

Special Relativity and Kinetic Energy

It was noted above that kinetic energy is velocity dependent. Kinetic energy follows from special relativity which is linked to $-Et+px$ which is the classical action which also yields quantum results. Thus $E=mc/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} = mc + .5mv^2$ to first order. In other words kinetic energy is an intrinsic part of the energy of a particle with momentum p because $p=Ev/c$ in special relativity. Thus even though the potential interaction is strictly momentum based $V(x)$ represents energy and energy associated with a particle with momentum p must include velocity which is time or rate based. It is just masked through $v=p/m_0$ (nonrelativistically).

Rest Mass

As argued above, quantum mechanical bound state problems are usually solved in a special frame, namely the rest frame of the potential $V(x)$. The potential may be created by a particle with a large rest mass M_1 , but the second particle has a rest mass m_2 and is moving. In the nonrelativistic case, that is fine because kinetic energy is the first order correction to the relativistic energy $E=mc/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ ($c=1$). Thus when one solves for E_n this is essentially an energy in the rest frame and so it is equivalent to a "rest mass" or binding energy. Thus: $-E_n t + 0x$ describes a rest frame binding energy with no overall momentum. One may then consider a system with energy $M_1c^2 + m_2c^2 - E_n$ and apply a Lorentz transformation to this 4-vector. E_n , however, is calculated in the special frame in which $V(x)$ is stationary.

Conclusion

In conclusion, quantum mechanics seems to be closely linked to special relativity on the one hand by using $E=mc/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ or $E=mc + .5mv^2$ to first order a velocity dependent result. On the other hand, bound state problems are usually solved in a special frame, namely the rest frame of $V(x)$, the potential. Thus the energy found is a kind of rest mass (i.e. binding energy). One may add $M_1c^2 + m_2c^2 + E_n$ to find an overall system rest mass and use this with 0 momentum to create a four-vector even though E_n has been specifically found in the rest frame of $V(x)$.

A distinguishing feature of quantum mechanics seems to be that $V(x)$ interacts only through momentum. In other words for $p_1=m_1v_1=p_2=m_2v_2$, there are certainly different velocities and times, but the same two slit interference pattern results. We argued in (1) that $-Et+px=A$ = classical action for a free particle should be treated with t and x being completely separate. Thus there would be a strictly p related term px which could not distinguish between different velocities. We argued that p scales x and that one may use dA/dx partial = p to create an eigenvalue equation such that $-i\hbar/dx$ partial $\exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. Such a probabilistic term would allow for

momentum only interaction with $V(x)$. In such a case there is no following of a particle in space time as it interacts. This means that even free motion is linked to $\exp(ipx)$ and there can be interference as in the average kinetic energy calculation of a quantum bound state.

For a quantum bound state, energy from special relativity necessarily involves v i.e. $E = m_0c^2 + .5mv^2$ has $.5mv^2 = .5pv$. Thus velocity or time/rate is explicitly present, it is just masked using $v=p/m_0$ (nonrelativistically). A first difference from classical mechanics is that the force does not explicitly change v in a region dx . Rather $V(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ interacts through momentum to create a potential energy for each p (based on interactions with the whole range of momenta), but this energy is added to the v dependent $.5pv$ $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to obtain an overall constant E_n $a(p)\exp(ipx)$. A second difference is that free motion contains more information than the classical mechanical scenario which has m_0 , and $v=dx/dt$. The quantum particle has both of these, but also a phase px linked to $\exp(ipx)$ which represents two sets of shifted (in space and hence in time) probability distributions. This is more complicated than $x=vt$, but creates the illusion of $x=vt$ because the modulus of $\exp(ipx)=1$. For a free particle that does not interact, $\exp(ipx)$ does not manifest itself and one has p , $pp/2m$, v at each point, but really even free motion is linked to $\exp(ipx)$ and interference of free terms i.e $a(p) .5pv \exp(ipx)$ occurs and in this case acceleration is the created illusion (or mathematical average) for all bound state energy levels.

Perhaps surprisingly, quantum mechanics arises out of the Lorentz invariant $A=-Et+px$ (classical action) by usually choosing the rest frame of the potential $V(x)$ and breaking A into two independent pieces $-Et$ and px . In such a case, E scales time and p space and it is argued that this is physically manifested. It is as if one is “breaking” the Lorentz invariant, yet $p=m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $E = m_0 + .5mv^2$ both come from relativistic considerations and appear in bound state calculations. Using $\exp(ipx)$ an $v=p/m_0$ (nonrelativistically) is a way to convert all time dependent pieces (if $V(x)$ or $V(x,v)$) into m_0 -momentum-space related ones. It should be noted, however, that even if one has interference in $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, if an impulse occurs it is linked to a specific p which is governed by special relativity and not $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ simply gives a probability profile, but does not change the $m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv}$ nature of momentum.

Thus the form $\exp(ipx)$ has a modulus of 1 suggesting the “illusion” of a smooth space in terms of probability. $x=vt$ holds in this space and it is this space which is linked to special relativity, but it seems reality is really about a dynamically changing $\cos(px)$ distribution which together with $\sin(px)$ in a second dimension describes a physical momentum wave which travels with the particle moving with the illusory smooth velocity of v . Even in the case of a free particle $\exp(ipx)$, the phase px is being tracked.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. **Phase and Group Velocity with a Free Particle Action**(preprint, zenodo, 2022)